

The study "Urgency of Asbabun Nuzul and Contribution in Understanding the Qur'an"

Mukhlis

STAI Al-Jami Banjarmasin, Indonesia

mukhlisahmadmuaidi@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to know the analysis of the urgency and contribution of the study on Asbabun Nuzul in understanding the Quran. Asbabun Nuzul, or the reasons for the revelation of the verses of the Quran, plays a crucial role in the context of interpreting and understanding the sacred verses. The research employs the method of literature or library research, conducted by gathering information from existing sources such as books, journals, articles, and other publications related to the research topic. In this study, the author explores how understanding the historical and situational context of the verses of the Quran can enrich interpretation and its application in daily life. Through an analytical approach, the author highlights the urgency of studying Asbabun Nuzul to avoid errors and misunderstandings in interpreting the verses of the Quran. Based on the research findings, it is revealed that understanding Asbabun Nuzul is essential for comprehending the verses and avoiding misinterpretations. It helps to specify laws based on the reasons for revelation and provides clarity to the verses. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the development of more holistic and contextual methods of interpreting the Quran, enriching the understanding of the Muslim community towards the Quran..

Keywords: Urgency, Contribution, Qur'an, Asbabun nuzul.

A. INTRODUCTION

Asbab al-nuzul is a study in the science of the Qur'an that deals with the reasons for the revelation of a verse in the Qur'an. A verse cannot be understood correctly except by understanding the circumstances of its revelation. Therefore, by examining the reasons for the revelation of a verse, it will provide an explanation of the legal rulings associated with it.¹

The Qur'an is indeed regarded as a guidance for humanity (hudan lil-nas), laying down fundamental principles for all aspects of human life. It serves as a universal book, providing the foundational principles of the Islamic faith and

¹ Andri Syahputra and Agustiar Agustiar, "Urgensi Asbabun Nuzul Dalam Mengatasi Pemahaman Takfiri: Kajian Ayat-Ayat Takfir Dalam Al-Qur'an," *Al-Amin: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Dan Sosial Humaniora* 1, no. 1 (2023): H.19, <https://ejournal.staialkifayahriau.ac.id/index.php/alamin/article/view/231>.

serving as a life guide for its followers, ensuring happiness both in this world and the hereafter.²

The Qur'an, as the sacred book of Islam, serves as the primary source of guidance for life, encompassing spiritual, ethical, and legal values. A profound understanding of the verses of the Qur'an is essential for Muslims in navigating their lives. In the effort to comprehend the meanings and messages within the Qur'anic verses, the study of Asbabun Nuzul, or the reasons for the revelation of these verses, emerges as a critical aspect in the interpretation process.

The importance of understanding the historical and situational context behind the revelation of the verses of the Qur'an cannot be overlooked. The reasons for the revelation provide a more comprehensive picture of the meaning and purpose of the Divine revelation. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the urgency and contribution of the study of Asbabun Nuzul in opening the door to a broader understanding of the Qur'an.

Through an analytical approach, this study will review how an understanding of Asbabun Nuzul can enrich the interpretation of the verses of the Qur'an and avoid misconceptions in interpretation. Thus, it is expected that this study will make a significant contribution to the development of a more holistic and contextual method of interpreting the Qur'an.

The Qur'an is the word of Allah, revealed to Prophet Muhammad through the Angel Gabriel in both its wording and meaning. It holds the position as the primary and foremost source of all Islamic teachings, serving as guidance for humanity to attain happiness in both the worldly life and the hereafter.

The Qur'an is Allah's revelation bestowed upon Prophet Muhammad, distinct in that it is not conveyed by the Angel Gabriel, nor is it the direct speech of Allah. Instead, it is the divine revelation articulated in the language of the Prophet himself.

There are many tools to understand verses or passages in the Qur'an. For instance, being the last Prophet and thus, not mentioned in the Qur'an, Hadith is one such tool. Others include 'Ilm I'rab Al-Qur'an, 'Ilm Garib Al-Qur'an, 'Ilm Awqat an-Nuzul, 'Ilm Asbab an-Nuzul, and so on. 'Ilm Asbab an-Nuzul is among the highly important methods in understanding and interpreting the Qur'an. As scholars have established, the Qur'an was revealed in two parts. One part was revealed directly and constitutes the majority of the Qur'an. The second part was revealed in response to specific events or requests, accompanying the revelation over thirteen years. This second part is what will be discussed based on the reasons for its revelation. Knowing the reasons for revelation and the details surrounding the text will aid in understanding what is intended by the text itself.

3

² M Junaid, "SEJARAH AL-QUR'AN: FENOMENA PEWAHYUAN DAN PEMBUKUAN AL-QUR'AN SERTA ASBABUN NUZUL," *Al-Muaddib: Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial Dan Keislaman* 7, no. 1 (2022): H. 36, <http://jurnal.um-tapsel.ac.id/index.php/al-muaddib/article/view/6924>.

³ Yusuf Al-Qardawi, *Bagaimana Berinteraksi Dengan Al-Qur'an*, Terj. Kathur Suhardi, vol. 7 (Jakarta: Pustaka al-Kausar, 2021), H. 267.

B. METHOD

This research employs a literature or library research method, which is conducted using literature such as books and other scholarly works. The data utilized in this study includes journals and books related to Asbabun Nuzul.

This library research involves gathering information from existing sources such as books, journals, articles, and other publications related to the research topic. By doing so, the researcher can comprehend the latest developments in the field and build a strong knowledge foundation before initiating their own research.

In this research, the author employs descriptive research, focusing more on the strength of analyzing existing sources and data. The approach relies on established theories and concepts to interpret information based on writings that contribute to the discussion.⁴

Based on the search conducted on various articles, journals, and other scholarly works related to the predetermined keywords, the researcher then gathers and selects information to draw conclusions that will serve as references for the research writing.

C. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Asbabun Nuzul refers to the reasons or events that underlie the revelation of Quranic verses. Asbabun Nuzul holds significant meaning in interpreting the Qur'an. One cannot attain a good understanding without understanding the historical context or the reasons behind the revelation of a particular verse.⁵

Asbabun Nuzul is a historical material that can be used to provide information about the revelation of the verses of the Quran and offer context to understand His commands. Certainly, these materials only cover events that occurred during the time when the Quran was being revealed (ashr at-tanzil). The urgency of understanding Asbabun Nuzul is an obligation for Muslims. The foundational knowledge of Asbabun Nuzul can be oriented to strengthen the faith and piety of a Muslim in adhering steadfastly to the guidance of Islam, namely the Quran itself.⁶

The urgency and contribution of Asbabun Nuzul in understanding the Qur'an cannot be overstated. The study of the reasons for the revelation of these sacred verses serves as a crucial foundation in avoiding misunderstandings of the Qur'anic verses. By comprehending the historical and situational context in which these verses were revealed, Muslims can deepen their understanding. Asbabun Nuzul opens the door to delve into the wisdom of Divine revelation, providing a more comprehensive insight into the purpose and wisdom of Allah. Furthermore, the contribution of Asbabun Nuzul is evident in the context of the Prophet's life, offering a unique perspective on the everyday situations of that time. This study is not only a historical exploration but also leads to explanations of the laws and ethics contained in the Qur'an. Understanding the reasons for the revelation of

⁴ Rita Kumala Sari, "Penelitian Kepustakaan Dalam Penelitian Pengembangan Pendidikan Bahasa Indonesia," *Jurnal Borneo Humaniora* 4, no. 2 (2021): 60–69.

⁵ Prifianza Verda Kirana, "Asbabun Nuzul Dan Urgensinya Dalam Memahami Makna Alqur'an," *EDUCATIA: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Dan Agama Islam* 12, no. 1 (2022): H. 27, <https://jurnal.educatia.id/ojs3/index.php/educatia/article/view/6>.

⁶ Nisfu Kurniyatillah, Mahmud Arif, and Mohamad Syawaluddin, "Eksistensi Asbabun Nuzul Dan Tafsir Ilmi Dalam Al-Qur'an," *AN NUR: Jurnal Studi Islam* 15, no. 1 (2023): H. 103, <https://jurnalannur.ac.id/index.php/An-Nur/article/view/438>.

verses helps connect these laws to specific contexts, providing a broader view of the application of Islamic values. Moreover, the contribution of Asbabun Nuzul is not confined to the past but has strong relevance in contemporary contexts. The application of principles revealed through Asbabun Nuzul can guide Muslims in facing modern challenges and ensure the authenticity and relevance of the sacred verses in daily life.

Understanding the Qur'an cannot be separated from comprehending the historical and situational context in which its verses were revealed. This is the urgency of studying Asbabun Nuzul. Without this understanding, the risk of misunderstandings and incorrect interpretations of the sacred verses is significantly high.

Thus, the urgency and contribution of Asbabun Nuzul in understanding the Qur'an are not merely a historical study but also a key to preserving the authenticity and relevance of the sacred verses in every aspect of the lives of the Muslim community. In making decisions, including determining laws, it is not just about making decisions for the sake of making them. Therefore, studying or understanding the science of Asbabun Nuzul is crucial for a Muslim to know the reasons behind the revelation of the Qur'anic verses and comprehend the content of the verses they seek to understand.⁷

Thus, the Qur'an, created by Allah, is clearly intended to serve as a guide for humanity, showing them the righteous path to follow. This is to enable individuals to lead their lives in accordance with the messages, strengthening their faith in Allah. The Qur'an did not descend into a culturally void society. Numerous verses of the Qur'an, according to scholars, must be understood in the context of Asbabun Nuzul. Asbabun Nuzul represents empirical historical conditions or events that underlie the revelation of a verse and is not something that is inherently absolute, such as a law of causality. This means that Asbabun Nuzul is not understood in terms of quality. So, in the context of Asbabun Nuzul, it cannot be interpreted that without Asbabun Nuzul, no verses would have been revealed, as the verses of the Qur'an are not a direct result of the underlying causes. This article will discuss Asbabun Nuzul as a dialogue between the text and reality.

1. The urgency of Asbabun Nuzul in understanding the Qur'an

Understanding the Quran is not enough by merely reading the text in a raw or what we call a textual manner. Because there is a significant possibility of misinterpretation in comprehending the true content of the Quran. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct research on the Asbab an-Nuzul with a descriptive analysis approach to the Quran, which involves looking at the circumstances or situations "when the Quran was revealed and what accompanied it in the environment or place where the Quran was sent down." The aim is to attain genuine correctness in interpreting what is contained in the Quran.⁸

One crucial aspect of Quranic studies is the discussion of *Asbāb al-Nuzūl*. *Asbāb al-Nuzūl* refers to historical materials that can be used as references to provide explanations for the verses of the Quran, offering clear information about

⁷ Didin Saefudin Buchori, *Pedoman Memahami Kandungan Al-Qur'an* (Bogor: Granada Pustaka, 2018), H. 34.

⁸ Adrian Adrian, Novi Andriani, and Umi Nurhayati, "Urgensi Asbab An-Nuzul Sebagai Langkah Awal Untuk Menafsirkan Al-Qur'an," *Indo-MathEdu Intellectuals Journal* 4, no. 2 (2023): H. 646, <https://www.indo-intellectual.id/index.php/imeij/article/view/229>.

the context to facilitate a better understanding of its commandments during the time when the Quran was revealed.⁹

The study of Asbab al-Nuzul, or the reasons for the revelation of the verses of the Quran, holds undeniable importance in understanding and interpreting the Islamic holy book. Understanding the historical and situational context in which these verses were revealed plays a crucial role in avoiding misunderstandings and incorrect interpretations.

Firstly, this urgency materializes in the effort to prevent misunderstandings of the verses of the Quran. By understanding the reasons for their revelation, the Islamic community can avoid narrow and overly detailed interpretations, ensuring that the sacred verses are understood in accordance with their true intentions.

Furthermore, Asbab al-Nuzul enables the Islamic community to delve into the meanings of the verses of the Quran through a historical and contextual perspective. This provides a deeper dimension to the divine messages, enriching the spiritual and intellectual understanding of the community.

Moreover, the urgency of Asbab al-Nuzul is reflected in its ability to open a window into the life of Prophet Muhammad and the conditions of society at that time. By understanding its concrete situations, the Islamic community can relate Islamic teachings to the challenges and everyday realities faced by the Prophet and his people. Lastly, Asbab al-Nuzul provides a strong foundation for interpreting Islamic laws and ethics. Knowing the reasons behind the revelation of legal verses allows the Islamic community to apply these principles in a contextual and relevant manner in modern life. Thus, the urgency of Asbab al-Nuzul is not only historical but also opens the door to a deeper and more applicable understanding of Quranic teachings in various aspects of life.

Understanding the context of the revelation of verses through the study of Asbab al-Nuzul is highly beneficial. It is crucial for applying the verses in different cases and situations. The likelihood of misunderstandings increases significantly when the history of Asbab al-Nuzul is overlooked. The benefits of the knowledge of Asbab al-Nuzul include, firstly, gaining insight into the wisdom behind the divine laws revealed for specific reasons. Secondly, understanding the individuals or events preceding the revelation of a particular verse. Thirdly, determining whether a verse conveys a specific or general message and the circumstances under which it should be applied. Fourthly, drawing the conclusion that Allah always pays attention to the prophets and is always with His servants.¹⁰

Asbab al-Nuzul, or the reasons for the revelation of the verses of the Quran, constitutes an integral part of the study of interpretation and understanding of the Islamic holy book. Its significance lies in its ability to present the historical and situational context behind each verse, enabling the Islamic community to interpret and apply the teachings of Allah more accurately.

Asbab al-Nuzul helps to avoid misunderstandings of the verses of the Quran. The specific historical context provides a deeper understanding of the meaning and purpose of divine revelation, preventing incorrect interpretations. Additionally, this study also offers a more comprehensive picture of the life of

⁹ Herni Herni, Helda Helda, and Hayatun Nida, "MEMAHAMI MAKNA DAN URGENSI ASBAB ANNUZUL QURAN," *MUSHAF JOURNAL: Jurnal Ilmu Al Quran Dan Hadis* 2, no. 2 (2022): H. 160, <https://mushafjournal.com/index.php/mj/article/view/30>.

¹⁰ Prifianza Verda Kirana, "Asbabun Nuzul Dan Urgensinya Dalam Memahami Makna Alqur'an," *EDUCATIA: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Dan Agama Islam* 12, no. 1 (2022): H. 33, <https://jurnal.educatia.id/ojs3/index.php/educatia/article/view/6>.

Prophet Muhammad and the specific circumstances of that time. By understanding the social, political, and economic conditions when the verses were revealed, the Islamic community can relate these teachings to the specific challenges faced by Prophet Muhammad and his people during that era.

Asbab al-Nuzul also makes a significant contribution to interpreting Islamic laws and ethics. By knowing the reasons for the revelation of the verses, the Islamic community can better apply these principles in the context of everyday life.

Lastly, the urgency of Asbab al-Nuzul is not confined to the past; this study opens the door to bridging traditional understanding with modern challenges. By reflecting on the reasons for the revelation of the verses, the Islamic community can unearth principles that remain relevant and applicable in contemporary contexts, ensuring that the teachings of Allah continue to be a living and relevant guide.

Asbab al-Nuzul consists of two words, namely 'asbab' and 'nuzul.' 'Asbab' is the plural form of the word 'sebab,' meaning reasons or causes. Meanwhile, the word 'nuzul' is the base form of 'nazala-yanzilu-nuzulan,' which means to descend or come down. Linguistically, 'Asbab al-Nuzul' translates to the reasons for the descent of something. In terms of terminology, it refers to something for which a verse or several verses were revealed, containing the reasons for it, providing an answer to those reasons, or explaining the laws related to the events at the time of its occurrence.¹¹

The basic guidance for scholars in determining Asbab al-Nuzul is through authentic narrations originating from Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) or his companions. This is because when a companion reports such information, if it is clear (sharih), it is not merely an opinion (ra'yi), but it holds the status of a marfu ruling (attributed to the Prophet). Al-Wahidi states, 'It is not permissible to speculate about the Asbab al-Nuzul of Quranic verses except based on narrations or direct hearing from those who witnessed the revelation, knew its reasons, discussed its understanding, and earnestly sought it.' This is the approach taken by the early scholars. They were extremely cautious about making statements regarding Asbab al-Nuzul without clear knowledge.¹²

Asbab al-Nuzul is a crucial topic in the field of Ulum al-Qur'an because understanding it can help unravel the secrets within the Quran, shedding light on its mysteries.

Terminologically, according to Az-Zarqani in his book 'Manahil al-'Urfan fi 'Ulum Al-Qur'an,' the understanding of Asbab al-Nuzul is something that causes the revelation of one or several verses to discuss the reasons or explain the laws related to those reasons at the time of their occurrence.¹³

Subhi As-Salih interprets it as follows: something that becomes the cause for the revelation of a verse or several verses, or a question that becomes the

¹¹ Abd Rojak and Aminuin, *Studi Ilmu al- Qur'an* (Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media, 2018), H. 67.

¹² Muhyidin Muhyidin and M Fathor Rohman, "Urgensi Asbab An-Nuzul Dalam Penafsiran Ayat-Ayat Al-Qur'an," *Ummul Qura Jurnal Institut Pesantren Sunan Drajat (INSUD) Lamongan* 17, no. 1 (2022): H. 56, <https://www.ejournal.insud.ac.id/index.php/UQ/article/view/135>.

¹³ Az-Zarqani, *Manahil al-'Urfan fi 'Ulum Al-Qur'an* (Al-Qahirah: Dar al-Hadis, 2018), H. 95.

reason for the revelation of a verse as an answer, or as an explanation revealed at the time of a particular event.¹⁴

Meanwhile, Hasbi Ash-Siddieqy defines it as an event for which the Quran was revealed to explain its laws on the day the events occurred, capturing the atmosphere in which the Quran was revealed. It discusses the reasons for that event, whether it was revealed immediately after the occurrence or later due to a certain wisdom.¹⁵

From various definitions and understandings, it is observed that the reasons for the revelation of a verse can sometimes take the form of events and at other times take the form of questions. A verse or several verses may be revealed to explain matters related to events or to provide answers to specific questions. The reasons for the revelation of a verse in the form of events can be classified into three types,¹⁶ namely:

a. Khusumah Incident (Quarrel)

Namely, events that are ongoing, such as the conflict between the Aus and Khazraj groups incited by the provocations of the Jewish community, leading them to shout "as-silah, as-silah," which means weapons, weapons. Because of this event, several verses from Surah Ali Imran, specifically verse 100, were revealed.

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِن تَطِيعُوا فَرِيقًا مِّنَ الَّذِينَ أُوتُوا الْكِتَابَ يَرُدُّوكُم بَعْدَ إِيمَانِكُمْ كُفْرِينَ

O you who have believed, if you follow some of those who were given the Scripture, they will turn you back, after your belief, into disbelievers

Until the following verses, which warn these two tribes to avoid disunity and hostility and remind them to maintain love, unity, and solidarity.¹⁷

b. The incident was a fatal mistake

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَقْرَبُوا الصَّلَاةَ وَأَنتُمْ سُكَارَىٰ حَتَّىٰ تَعْلَمُوا مَا تَقُولُونَ

"O you who believe, do not pray while you are drunk, until you understand what you are saying."

In a history it is stated that Abdurrahman bin Auf invited Ali and his friends to eat, then served them khamr (Arak, liquor), so that their brains were

¹⁴ Subhi As-Salih, *Membahas Ilmu-Ilmu Al-Qur'an, Terjemahan. Tim Pustaka Firdaus*, 18th ed. (Jakarta: Pustaka Firdaus, 2018), H. 160.

¹⁵ Hasbi Ash-Shiddieqy, *Sejarah dan Pengantar Ilmu Al-Qur'an/Tafsir*, vol. III (Jakarta: Bulan Bintang, 2018), H. 78.

¹⁶ Ridhoul Wahidi, "ASBABUN NUZUL SEBAGAI CABANG ULUMUL QUR'AN," *SYAHADAH: Jurnal Ilmu al-Qur'an Dan Keislaman* 3, no. 1 (2021): H. 56, <https://doi.org/10.32520/syhd.v3i1.148>.

¹⁷ Syukraini Ahmad, "ASBAB NUZUL (Urgensi Dan Fungsinya Dalam Penafsiran Ayat Al-Qur'an)," *El-Afkar: Jurnal Pemikiran Keislaman Dan Tafsir Hadis* 7, no. 2 (2021): H. 96.

disturbed. When it was time for prayer, the people asked Ali to be the imam, and when he read the wrong verse.¹⁸

c. These events are in the form of ideals and desires

One important aspect of Quranic studies is the discussion of *Asbāb al-nuzūl*. *Asbāb al-nuzūl* consists of historical materials that can be referenced to provide explanations for the verses of the Quran, clearly offering information about the context to facilitate understanding of its commandments during the time when the Quran was revealed.¹⁹

Such as conforming the provisions of Umar Bin Khattab to the provisions of the verses of the Koran. In history, there are several hopes that Umar expressed to the Prophet Muhammad SAW. Then the verse contained in it was revealed in accordance with Umar's expectations. Some scholars have written about it specifically. For example, Imam Al-Bukhari and others narrated from Anas ra. that Umar said: "I agree with my Lord on three things: I said to the Messenger, what if we made Ibrahim's grave a place of prayer." Then the word of Allah SWT came down:

وَاتَّخِذُوا مِنْ مَّقَامِ إِبْرَاهِيمَ مُصَلًّىً

"And make the maqam of Ibrahim a place of prayer".

As for the verses revealed in response to questions posed to Prophet Muhammad (SAW), there are also three forms. These questions may be related to the past, the present, or the future.

First, questions about past events are found in the word of Allah SWT in surah Al-Kahf verse 83:

وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ ذِي الْقُرْنَيْنِ قُلْ سَأَتْلُوا عَلَيْكُمْ مِنْهُ ذِكْرًا

"They will ask you (Muhammad) about Zulkarnain. Say: "I will read to you the story of the challenge."

Say: "I will read to you the story of the challenge."

Second, questions about current events are found in the word of Allah SWT in surah Al-Isra' verse 85:

وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الرُّوحِ قُلِ الرُّوحُ مِنْ أَمْرِ رَبِّي وَمَا أُوتِيتُمْ مِنَ الْعِلْمِ إِلَّا قَلِيلًا

¹⁸ Fa'iqo Kumalasari, *ASBABUN NUZUL Turunnya Al-Qur'an* (SURABAYA: UIN SUNAN AMPEL, 2020), H. 9, https://www.academia.edu/download/67457707/Fa_iqo_Kumalasari_04010120009_A1.pdf.

¹⁹ Herni Herni, Helda Helda, and Hayatun Nida, "MEMAHAMI MAKNA DAN URGENSI ASBAB ANNUZUL QURAN," *MUSHAF JOURNAL: Jurnal Ilmu Al Quran Dan Hadis* 2, no. 2 (2022): H. 160, <https://mushafjournal.com/index.php/mj/article/view/30>.

“And they ask you about spirits. Say: "The Spirit is part of the business of my Lord, and you have not been given knowledge but a little." Say: "The Spirit is part of the business of my Lord, and you have not been given knowledge but a little.”

Third, the question about future events is found in surah An-Nazi'at verse 42:

يَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ السَّاعَةِ أَيَّانَ مُرْسَاهَا

“(The disbelievers) ask you (Muhammad) about the day of resurrection, when it will occur.”

Say: "Indeed, knowledge of the Hour is with my Lord. None can reveal its time except Him. It is heavy in the heavens and the earth. It will not come upon you except unexpectedly." They ask you as if you are familiar with it..

Say: "Indeed, knowledge of the Day of Resurrection is with Allah, but most people do not know."²⁰

2. **Asbabun Nuzul's contribution to understanding the Qur'an**

Understanding the reasons for revelation (asbabun nuzul) is crucial for grasping the context in which the verses were revealed. This is especially important for applying the verses to different cases and situations. The likelihood of misunderstanding increases if the historical context of the reasons for revelation is overlooked. The benefits of knowledge about asbabun nuzul include: first, one can discern the wisdom behind the legislation revealed through specific circumstances. Second, one can identify the individuals or parties involved in the events preceding the revelation of a particular verse. Third, one can determine whether a verse contains a specific or general message and under what circumstances it should be appropriately applied. Fourth, one can conclude that Allah always pays attention to the messengers and is always with His servant.²¹

The contribution of Asbabun Nuzul, or the causes of the revelation of the verses of the Qur'an, in the understanding of the Islamic holy book is very significant. By examining the historical and situational context behind each verse, Asbabun Nuzul makes a valuable contribution in interpreting and applying the teachings of the Qur'an.

First, the main contribution of Asbabun Nuzul lies in its ability to provide a more comprehensive picture of the meaning and purpose of Divine revelation. By understanding the historical background in which the verses were revealed, the Islamic community can unearth deeper and contextual meanings of each revelation.

Furthermore, Asbabun Nuzul contributes to detailing the everyday life of the Prophet Muhammad and the specific challenges he faced. This opens a

²⁰ Nispul Khoiri, *Ilmu-Ilmu Studi Al-Qur'an* (Medan: Perdana Publishing, 2020), H. 56.

²¹ Prifianza Verda Kirana, "Asbabun Nuzul Dan Urgensinya Dalam Memahami Makna Al-Qur'an," *EDUCATIA: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Dan Agama Islam* 12, no. 1 (2022): H. 33, <https://jurnal.educatia.id/ojs3/index.php/educatia/article/view/6>.

window into the social, political, and economic context of that time, enabling the Islamic community to connect Islamic teachings with the real-life situations encountered by the Prophet and the Muslim community at that time.

Another contribution lies in elucidating Islamic law and ethics. By understanding the reasons behind the revelation of specific verses, the Islamic community can recognize the foundations and principles underlying Islamic law, ensuring that interpretations and applications align with the relevant historical context

Lastly, Asbabun Nuzul brings a contemporary contribution by actualizing the teachings of the Qur'an in the context of modern times. A profound understanding of the reasons behind the revelation of verses enables the Islamic community to apply these values wisely and relevantly in facing the challenges and changes of the times. Thus, the contribution of Asbabun Nuzul is not only in historical understanding but also serves as a key to bridging traditional understanding with the modern context, ensuring that the teachings of the Qur'an remain a source of inspiration and relevant guidance in the lives of the Islamic community.

Furthermore, the categorization of Quranic verses in terms of Asbabun Nuzul has at least three possibilities as to why not all verses of the Quran can be known for the reasons behind their revelation, and each of these possibilities is closely related to one another.

The first possibility is that not all aspects related to the process of the Quranic revelation are covered by the companions who directly witnessed the descent of the Quranic revelations.

Secondly, the witnessing of the companions regarding matters related to the process of the descent of the Quranic revelations is not entirely documented. Even if later recorded, the recording itself can be considered delayed. Therefore, even if the entire process of the Quranic revelation is recorded by the companions, there might be gaps in their memory due to the delay in recording.

Thirdly, it is widely open to the possibility that there are a number of verses of the Quran whose revelation is considered appropriate without being directly associated with a specific event to identify the reasons for the revelation of the verse. This can be traced through various exegesis books or through preceding questions.²²

3. The way to find out Asbabun Nuzul

The main foundation for scholars in understanding Asbabun Nuzul is the authenticity of the narration from the Prophet Muhammad or from the companions. If the information comes solely from the companions, then the report should be explicit and transparent. Reports from the companions hold a higher legal status. According to al-Wahidi, relying solely on statements is not permissible in terms of Asbabun Nuzul; instead, it should be based on narration or firsthand accounts from those who conveyed the revelation. These individuals stand on the grounds of reasons for revelation, responding with their knowledge and obtaining what they seek.²³

Al-Wahidi stated that one should not speak about the reasons for the revelation of the Quran except based on narrations and information heard

²² Muhammad Amin Suma, *Ulumul Qur'an* (Jakarta: Rajawali Pers, 2021), H. 209.

²³ Halimuddin, *Pembahasan Ilmu Al-Qur'an* (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2021), H. 85.

directly from individuals who witnessed the descent of those verses, knew the reasons for their revelation, and discussed their understanding.²⁴

Muhammad bin Sirin said, "I asked Ubaidah about the verses of the Quran. He replied, 'Fear Allah and speak the truth. Those who knew about the circumstances of the revelation have passed away.'"

Based on the information above, if the reasons for revelation (Asbabun Nuzul) are narrated by a companion, it can be accepted (maqbul) even if it is not strengthened and supported by other narrations. This is because the words of a companion leave no room for personal interpretation in this matter, and companions are individuals who directly witnessed and met the Prophet Muhammad. As for if the reasons for revelation are narrated through a Mursal hadith, which is a hadith whose chain lacks a companion and only reaches a Tabi'in, its status is not acceptable unless its chain is authentic and supported by another Mursal hadith. The narrator should be from the scholars of interpretation who derived their interpretations from the companions, such as Mujahid, Ikrimah, and Sa'id bin Jubair.²⁵

From this, it is clear that the way to know the reasons for revelation (Asbabun Nuzul) is through both authentic hadiths and Mursal hadiths, with the condition that the chain is authentic and must be strengthened by another Mursal hadith narrated by companions or Tabi'in. This is because companions are individuals who witnessed and directly met Prophet Muhammad.

The occurrence of the reasons for the revelation of verses is a historical event that took place during the time of Prophet Muhammad. Therefore, there is no other way to know it except through authentic narrations from individuals who witnessed or were present during the events. The possibility of personal reasoning (ijtihad) is not applicable and is not permitted. Attempting to deduce it using logic or reasoning is considered an action without a basis and without knowledge.²⁶

In addition to the evidence from the Quran, there is also a hadith narrated by al-Tirmidhi that emphasizes the prohibition of interpreting the Quran without a foundation of knowledge. In a hadith, Prophet Muhammad said:

مَنْ قَالَ فِي الْقُرْآنِ بِغَيْرِ عِلْمٍ فَلْيَتَّبِعُوا مَفْعَدَةَ مِنَ النَّارِ

Whoever speaks about (interprets) the Quran without knowledge, then his place is in the Hellfire..²⁷

Based on the above hadith, the early scholars tended to avoid interpreting verses that they were not familiar with. Yahya bin Sa'id, from Sa'id

²⁴ Al-Wahidi, *Asbab Nuzul Al-Qur'an* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al- 'Ilmiyah, 2021), H. 11.

²⁵ Az-Zarqani, *Manahil al-'Urfan fi 'Ulum Al-Qur'an*, H. 102.

²⁶ Fahd Abdurrahman Ar Rumi, *Ulumul Qur'an: Studi Kompleksitas al-Qur'an, terjemahan Amirul Hasan dan Muhammad Halabi* (Yogyakarta: Penerbit Titian Ilahi Press, 2018), H. 183.

²⁷ Muhammad Isa bin Saurah al-Turmudzi, *Sunan Al-Turmudzi*, 5th ed. (Beirut: Al-Maktabah al-'Ashriyah, 2018), H. 881.

bin Musayyab, narrated that if he was asked about the interpretation of Quranic verses, he would respond that he would not comment on anything in the Quran..²⁸

Although the reasons for revelation (asbab al-nuzul) are known through narrations attributed to Prophet Muhammad, not all narrations attributed to him are acceptable. The narrations that can be relied upon are those that meet specific criteria as established by the experts in hadith. Specifically, for the narration of the reasons for revelation, it should come from individuals who were directly involved in and experienced the events narrated at the time of the revelation. Narrations from Tabi'in that do not reference Prophet Muhammad and his companions are considered weak (da'if). Therefore, one cannot simply accept the opinion of an author that a particular verse was revealed under specific circumstances.²⁹ Therefore, knowledge about the person narrating the event is crucial..

4. Generality of Pronunciation and Specificity of Reason

When a verse is revealed in accordance with a general cause or a specific cause, the general ('am) is applied to its generality, and the specific (khas) to its specificity. For example, in the words of Allah:

وَسَيُجَنَّبُهَا الْأَتْقَى ﴿١٧﴾ الَّذِي يُؤْتِي مَالَهُ يَتَزَكَّى ﴿١٨﴾ وَمَا لِأَحَدٍ عِنْدَهُ مِنْ نِعْمَةٍ تُجْزَى ﴿١٩﴾ إِلَّا ابْتِغَاءَ وَجْهِ رَبِّهِ الْأَعْلَى ﴿٢٠﴾ وَلَسَوْفَ يَرْضَى ﴿٢١﴾

And those who are the most righteous will be kept away from it (Hell), the ones who spend their wealth (in Allah's cause) to purify themselves, not seeking any reward or thanks from anyone, but seeking only the approval of their Lord, the Most High. And soon they will be well-pleased.”

These verses were revealed regarding Abu Bakr because the word 'al-atqa' (the most righteous) in the morphological form of af'ala indicates the superlative, a preference accompanied by the definite article (al-'ahdiyah), signifying that the word it encompasses is known. Thus, it is specified for the person for whom the verse was revealed. Therefore, al-Wahidi said: 'al-atqa refers to Abu Bakr as-Siddiq, according to the interpretation of the scholars.³⁰

Regarding that, if the cause is specific while the revealed verse is in general terms, there is a difference of opinion among the scholars of jurisprudence regarding whether the consideration is based on the generality of the wording or the specificity of the cause.

Firstly, the majority of scholars argue that the applicable principle is 'ibrah bi 'umum al-lafzhi (consideration based on the generality of the wording). Examples include the revelation of the verse regarding zihar in the case of Salamah bin Sakhr, the verse of li'an in the matter of Hilal bin Umayyah, and also the verse about a woman stealing during the time of the Prophet. All these

²⁸ Ahmad Izzan, *Metodologi Ilmu Tafsir* (Bandung: Tafakkur, 2018), H. 78.

²⁹ M Quraish Shihab, *Sejarah dan 'Ulum al-Qur'an* (Jakarta: Penerbit Pustaka Firdaus, 2018), H. 81.

³⁰ Manna Khalil Al-Qattan, *Studi Ilmu-ilmu Qur'an, Terj. Mudzakir* (Bogor: Litera AntarNusa, 2018), H. 115.

incidents have a general application to everyone without exception, not limited to Salamah bin Shakhr, Hilal bin Umayyah, or the woman who stole during the time of the Prophet (as-Saraqah).³¹

Secondly, some scholars argue that the consideration should be based on the specificity of the cause (al-'ibrah bi khusus as-sabab). They comment that the cases of zihar, li'an, and the woman who stole during the time of the Prophet apply only to those specific individuals and not to others. Therefore, they suggest finding other evidence using qiyas (analogy).

5. **Asbabun Nuzul as a way to understand the meaning of the Qur'an**

The commentators (experts in exegesis) have paid attention to and provided specific discussions on the issue of Asbabun Nuzul in their books. Among them is Ali bin Madini, a scholar mentioned by Bukhari, and the famous work written by al-Wahidi titled "Asbab Nuzul Al-Qur'an." It is a misconception to think that knowing the reasons for revelation is useless. According to them, studying it is not merely following historical events. On the contrary, studying the reasons for revelation has several benefits.³²

Al-Wahidi stated that it is impossible to understand the interpretation of a verse without relying on the story and explanation of the reasons for its revelation. Ibn Daqiq al-Id also mentioned that explaining the reasons for revelation is a strong method in understanding the meanings of Quranic verses. Similarly, Ibn Taymiyyah argued that knowing the reasons for revelation aids in understanding a verse because knowledge of the as-sabab (cause) leads to understanding the al-musabbab (effect).

6. **Benefits of Knowing Asbabun Nuzul**

The benefits of knowing Asbabun Nuzul have several benefits as follows:

- a. Knowing the wisdom of enacting a law and the attention of the Shari'a to the public benefit in dealing with all events as a blessing for the people.³³
- b. Provides legal boundaries derived from the causes that occur, if the law is stated in general form.
- c. If the pronouncement that is revealed is general in nature and there are arguments indicating its specialization, then the existence of asbabun nuzul will limit the takhshish to only those other than the form of cause.³⁴
- d. That by knowing the Asbabun Nuzul verses of the Qur'an it will give meaning and eliminate difficulties or doubts in interpreting it.³⁵

7. **The Urgency of Asbabun Nuzul**

³¹ As-Suyuti, *Al-Itqan fi 'Ulum Al-Qur'an*, vol. 1 (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyah, 2018), H. 61.

³² Az-Zarkasyi, *Al-Burhan fi 'Ulum Al-Qur'an*, vol. 1 (Al-Qahirah: Maktabah Dar at-Turas, 2018), H. 22.

³³ Syaiful Arief, *ULUMUL QUR'AN UNTUK PEMULA, (Program Studi Ilmu Al-Qur'an dan Tafsir Fakultas Ushuluddin Insitut PTIQ (Jakarta, : Program Studi Ilmu Al-Qur'an dan Tafsir Fakultas Ushuluddin Insitut PTIQ Jakarta, 2021)*, H. 66.

³⁴ Muhammad Yunan, "Nuzulul Qur'an Dan Asbabun Nuzul," *Al-Mutsala* 2, no. 1 (2020): H. 58, <https://doi.org/10.46870/jstain.v2i1.33>.

³⁵ Yusep Ridwan, "Upaya meningkatkan pemahaman siswa pada pendalaman Al-qur'an melalui asbabun-nuzul, Universitas Islam Nusantara," *Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin* 1, no. 8 (November 2022): H. 763, <https://jurnal.arkainstitute.co.id/index.php/nautical/index>.

By knowing the reasons for the revelation (asbab al-nuzul) of a verse, it will have a significant impact in aiding the understanding of Quranic verses. It allows for a deeper understanding of the secrets behind the Quran's expression in explaining events. Therefore, anyone who is not aware of the reasons for the revelation of a verse can be assured that they will not comprehend the secrets concealed behind the Quran's manner of expressing its verses.³⁶

Understanding the reasons for revelation (asbab al-nuzul) has a significant impact on interpreting a person's text within the context of life. Therefore, without understanding the reasons for revelation, one can make mistakes in contextualizing Quranic verses. The urgency of knowing the reasons for revelation includes the following:

- a. Helps understand verses and avoids mistakes and difficulties.
- b. Specializing in law is limited to causes, especially scholars who adheres to the rule of "special cause".
- c. Provides clarity to the verse.
- d. Knowing the wisdom and secrets of enacting a law and paying attention to the public interest in dealing with an event.

Understanding whether a verse applies generally or specifically, Next, in what cases does this verse apply.³⁷

D. CONCLUSION

The urgency and contribution of Asbabun Nuzul in understanding the Quran are highly important and extensive. This study not only mitigates the potential for misunderstandings of sacred verses but also opens the door to a deeper, contextual, and relevant understanding of Divine teachings. Asbabun Nuzul provides a strong foundation to avoid narrow and incorrect interpretations of the Quran, reminding the Muslim community of the urgency of understanding the reasons for the revelation of each verse. Its contribution is evident in unveiling historical and situational contexts, enriching the spiritual and intellectual understanding of the community. Moreover, Asbabun Nuzul serves as a window connecting the Islamic community to the life of Prophet Muhammad and the society of that time, ensuring that Islamic teachings remain connected to daily challenges and realities. By knowing the reasons for the revelation of verses, Muslims can absorb the timeless and universal wisdom of Divine revelation.

Additionally, the contribution of Asbabun Nuzul extends to elucidating Islamic laws and ethics, ensuring that these principles are applied considering relevant historical contexts. In the contemporary era, a profound understanding of Asbabun Nuzul brings crucial contributions to actualizing the teachings of the Quran, making it a source of inspiration and relevant guidance in facing the challenges of the times. Thus, the urgency and contribution of Asbabun Nuzul not only weave back the relationship of the Islamic community with history and Divine revelation but also ensure that the Quran remains a living, adaptive, and relevant source of guidance in every journey of Muslim life.

³⁶ Muhammad Baqir Hakim, *Ulumul Quran, Diterjemahkan oleh Nashirul Haq, Abd.Ghafur, Salman Fadhullah* (Jakarta: Al-Huda, 2018), H. 39.

³⁷ Achmad Abu bakar, Ode Ismail Ahmad, and Yusuf Assagaf, *Ulumul Quran* (Yogyakarta: Semesta Aksara, 2019), H. 19.

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